

Sensitivity of OWC performance to air compressibility

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Abstract

Air compressibility is often neglected in experimental work due to practical difficulties, even though it is known to affect the performance of OWC wave energy converters. The key question, of course, is to what extent. In this work the impact of air compressibility on the capture width ratio is thoroughly quantified by means of a comprehensive experimental campaign, with no fewer than 330 tests encompassing a wide range of wave conditions and levels of turbine-induced damping, and two experimental set-ups: one designed to account for air compressibility, the other to neglect it. This approach is complemented with the use of the RANS-based CFD model OpenFOAM[®] to calibrate the pressure-vs-flowrate curves, which enables the flowrate to be determined based on the pressure drop measurements from the physical model. We find that the errors that derive from disregarding air compressibility may lead to either under- or over-predictions of power output, and are highly dependent on the operating conditions, more specifically the wave conditions (sea state) and turbine-induced damping.

Keywords

wave energy; wave power; oscillating water column; physical modelling; CFD; capture-width ratio

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, marine renewable energy has been identified as one of the renewable energy sources of greater potential, theoretically, enough to satisfy the global electric energy demand (Taveira-Pinto *et al.*, 2015). Among the different resources that integrate the marine renewables (waves, currents, tides, wind, thermal resources and salinity gradients), wave energy stands out by its

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29 high density and well-predictability (Arena *et al.*, 2015; Carballo *et al.*, 2015), its low environmental
30 impact (Iglesias and Carballo, 2014), and an exploitability that fully synergizes with other marine
31 renewable resources, such as offshore wind energy (Pérez-Collazo *et al.*, 2015), what enhances its
32 economic viability (Astariz and Iglesias, 2015). Despite the efforts made to design efficient and
33 reliable wave energy converters (WECs) (e.g., Contestabile *et al.*, 2017; López, M. *et al.*, 2017;
34 Stansby *et al.*, 2015), there is no technology at a commercial stage yet. Hence, technological
35 development is, doubtless, the key parameter for driving wave energy to the position that its potential
36 deserves.

37 Among the different types of technologies developed to harvest wave energy, oscillating water
38 column (OWC) devices (Falcão and Henriques, 2016) hold a prominent role. In fact, there are a
39 number of OWC converters that have reached the stage of full-scale prototypes (e.g., Arena *et al.*,
40 2013; Ibarra-Berastegi *et al.*, 2018). An OWC consists mainly in an air turbine and a hollow chamber,
41 partially submerged into the water and connected to the sea through an opening below the water
42 surface. Wave action produces the oscillation of the water column inside the chamber—giving name
43 to the device—and, subsequently, causes the alternating compression and decompression of the air
44 above the water surface, generating an air flow rate which impulses the turbine coupled to a generator.
45 Due to the bidirectional nature of the flow, a special air turbine design is needed. These self-rectifying
46 turbines can be classified according to their operational principle as reaction or impulse type turbines.
47 The reaction working principle has been applied to axial—the well-known Wells turbines
48 (Raghunathan, 1995), radial (Moisel, Christoph and Carolus, 2014) and mixed-flow (Moisel, C. and
49 Carolus, 2015) turbines. Similarly, both axial (Thakker *et al.*, 2004) and radial (Pereiras *et al.*, 2011)
50 impulse type turbines have been developed. A comprehensive overview on self-rectifying turbines can
51 be found in (Falcão and Gato, 2012).

52 The air pressure oscillations that takes place inside an OWC chamber and the subsequent air
53 flow between the chamber and the atmosphere constitute complex thermodynamic processes that
54 induce time-varying changes in air density. This spring-like effect of the air is known to significantly
55 affect the performance of an OWC converter, as was demonstrated by means of analytical ideal-gas
56 models, first, assuming an isentropic relationship between air pressure and density (Sarmiento and
57 Falcão, 1985), and then, more realistically, considering changes in entropy due to viscous losses
58 (Falcão and Justino, 1999). More recently, enhanced models based on the real-gas theory were also
59 developed (Medina-López *et al.*, 2017). However, although constitute an essential step in WEC

60 development, analytical models do not consider important non-linear effects (e.g., wave breaking,
61 viscosity or turbulence). Thus, physical or numerical models are a mandatory step in the design
62 process of any converter. Computational fluid dynamic (CFD) techniques have shown to be capable to
63 model OWC devices while accounting for all these effects (e.g., Elhanafi *et al.*, 2017; Simonetti *et al.*,
64 2018). Nevertheless, even the most advanced numerical models require a proper validation based on
65 physical model tests.

66 In small-scale experimental tests, an appropriate modelling of the spring-like effects of air
67 compressibility in the OWC chamber is not straightforward (Weber, 2007). In fact, to correctly
68 reproduce these thermodynamic effects while assuming fully geometric similarity would require to
69 control the ambient pressure to achieve a pressure ratio between model and prototype equal to the
70 length scale ratio (Falcão and Henriques, 2014; Weber, 2007). As pointed by those authors, a feasible
71 possibility to satisfy the scaling requirements of air compressibility is an appropriate adjustment of the
72 air chamber volume, i.e., to not match full geometric similarity, at least in the aerodynamic domain of
73 the OWC model. This is the methodology followed in the experimental model tests carried out by
74 Sarmiento (1993) and very recently by Perez-Collazo *et al.* (2018). However, despite the great amount
75 of works published over the last few years dealing with physical modelling of OWC converters (e.g.,
76 Ning *et al.*, 2016; Vyzikas, Deshoulières, Barton *et al.*, 2017), references where the air compressibility
77 effects are taken into account (if any) are scarcely found (Falcão and Henriques, 2016).

78 In this work, an extensive campaign of physical model tests was carried out in order to offer an
79 in-depth evaluation of the effects of the air compressibility on the performance of an OWC wave
80 energy converter, aiming to fully represent the complex physical relationships which other modelling
81 methodologies may not be able to simulate, i.e., without requiring an analytical simplification of the
82 governing processes. The testing campaign involved 330 tests, resulting from the combination of 55
83 regular wave conditions, three different levels of the turbine-induced damping and two set-up
84 configurations. The associated difficulties related to the consideration of the spring-like effect of the
85 air, required the use of numerical methods for calibrating the pressure-vs-flow-rate curves for the
86 different values of the turbine-induced damping. For this purpose, the open-source CFD code
87 OpenFOAM[®] was used as a complementary tool.

88 This paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, the materials and methods used to investigate
89 the effects of the air compressibility on the performance of the OWC are detailed. First, the physical
90 model campaign and its theoretical basis are presented. Second, the numerical model and its

91 characteristics (governing equations, computational domain, mesh and testing programme) are
 92 described. Last, the procedures to calculate the capture width ratio of the OWC are established. The
 93 results of the investigation are presented in Section 3, focusing on three main aspects: the validation
 94 of the numerical model; the pressure-vs-flow-rate curves of the orifices; and the analysis of the
 95 sensitivity of the OWC performance to air compressibility. Finally, conclusions are drawn in
 96 Section 4.

97 2. Materials and methods

98 2.1. Physical modelling

99 When designing a small-scale model of a wave energy converter—as in many other hydraulic
 100 applications in which free surface flows are involved—the Froude dynamic similitude criterion must
 101 be met (Hughes, 1993), i.e., equal Froude numbers in model and prototype. The Froude number (Fr)
 102 is defined as the ratio between the inertia (F_i) and gravity forces (F_g):

$$103 \quad Fr = \frac{F_i}{F_g} = \frac{v^2}{gL}, \quad (1)$$

104 where v is a characteristic velocity; g is the gravitational acceleration; and L is a characteristic length
 105 of the system.

106 In OWC systems, however, the air compression forces also play an important role. In analogy to
 107 the formulation of the Froude number, a non-dimensional number to characterise the compression
 108 forces can be formulated (Weber, 2007) as the ratio of the inertia forces (F_i) to the air compression
 109 forces (F_c):

$$110 \quad \frac{F_i}{F_c} = \frac{\rho v^2}{p_0 \gamma}, \quad (2)$$

111 where ρ is the fluid density; p_0 is the initial air pressure; and γ is the isentropic exponent. The
 112 simultaneous satisfaction of Eqs. (1) and (2) is far from straightforward and often impractical—it
 113 would require alterations of the fluid density or the control of the atmospheric pressure. The solution
 114 to overcome this (Falcão and Henriques, 2014) is to scale the air chamber volume according to:

$$115 \quad \frac{V_m}{V_p} = \frac{n_m}{n_p} \varepsilon^2 \delta^{-1}, \quad (3)$$

116 where the subscripts m and p refer to model scale and prototype, respectively; V is the air volume of
 117 the OWC chamber at still water level; n is the polytropic exponent of the turbine; ε is the length scale
 118 ratio (L_m/L_p); and δ is the water density ratio (ρ_m/ρ_p).

119 In sum, an OWC model must ensure that the Froude similitude criterion is met in the
 120 hydrodynamic domain (taking into account the maximum elevation that could be achieved by the free
 121 surface oscillations) where, in addition, perfect geometric similarity between model and prototype is
 122 required (Sheng, Wan *et al.*, 2014); and a distorted air chamber (in the aerodynamic domain) with a
 123 volume that satisfies Eq.(3).

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 125 Figure 1. Schematic of (A) a breakwater-integrated OWC, and 3D perspective (B) and views (C) of the
 126 model OWC.

127 The tested OWC model was designed following this methodology. It corresponds to a 1:25
 128 small-scale model of a regular design of breakwater-integrated OWC (Figure 1). A summary of the
 129 main dimensions of the model is presented in Table 1. It constitutes a 2D model in which the extra air
 130 chamber volume, needed to take into account the air compressibility effects, was achieved by
 131 connecting the chamber to an air reservoir of appropriate volume. This solution was successfully
 132 applied to other fixed-structure OWC devices (Sarmiento, 1993). In addition, using an air reservoir
 133 rather than a reshaped air chamber enables to assess the effects of the air compressibility on the
 134 performance of the OWC with one sole model, by connecting and disconnecting the air reservoir.

Table 1. Dimensions of the geometrical parameters of the OWC model

Geometrical parameter	Symbol	Model dimensions
Chamber height	h_c	63.6 cm
Chamber length (in the wave direction)	l_c	12.8 cm
Chamber width (transverse to wave direction)	w_c	65.0 cm
Entrance height	h_e	12.8 cm
Vertical walls thickness	t_z	2.0 cm
Horizontal walls thickness	t_x	2.8 cm
Orifice diameter	D	variable
Duct height	h_d	25D
Bedding height	h_b	8.0 cm
Bedding length	l_b	20.0 cm
Bedding slope	s	1:2

136 To simulate the turbine-induced damping—a critical variable in the performance of an OWC
 137 wave energy converter (López, I. *et al.*, 2014; Sheng, W. and Lewis, 2018)—an orifice was used,
 138 which emulates the quadratic pressure-versus-flow-rate relationship of a self-rectifying impulse
 139 turbine. In physical model tests, where the turbine can hardly be simulated by a small-scale turbine,
 140 using an orifice is a well-established method, in particular when dealing with scale factors below 1:10
 141 (Falcão and Henriques, 2014), although it has also been applied in large-scale experiments (Viviano *et*
 142 *al.*, 2016). Three different values of the turbine-induced damping were used by varying the orifice
 143 diameter ($D = 28, 31$ and 39 mm). These three orifice diameters correspond, approximately, to an area
 144 of 0.8%, 1.0% and 1.5% of the plan area of the chamber, respectively; values which are in consonance
 145 with previous works (López, I. *et al.*, 2015).

146 The polytropic exponent of a turbine is related to the turbine efficiency (η) by (e.g., Dixon and
 147 Hall, 2014):

$$148 \quad \eta = \frac{1 - (p_2/p_1)^{1-1/n}}{1 - (p_2/p_1)^{(\gamma-1)/\gamma}}, \quad (4)$$

149 where p_1 and p_2 are the pressures at the inlet and outlet of the turbine, respectively; and the isentropic
 150 exponent takes the value of $\gamma = 1.4$ for air. Therefore, the polytropic exponent is a function of the
 151 turbine efficiency and the pressure ratio (p_2/p_1). Falcão and Henriques (2014) have shown that the
 152 polytropic exponent is approximately constant with respect to the pressure ratio and varies depending
 153 on the turbine efficiency between $n = 1$ for the case in which no work is done by the turbine ($\eta = 0$)
 154 and $n = 1.4$ for a perfectly efficient turbine ($\eta = 1$). Thus, in the case of a turbine simulated by an
 155 orifice the polytropic exponent is $n = 1$. For a state-of-the-art full-size turbine, with an average
 156 efficiency of about $\eta = 0.6$, the polytropic exponent is approximately $n = 1.2$ (Falcão and Henriques,
 157 2016). Taking into account these values ($n_m = 1$ and $n_p = 1.2$) together with the dimensions of the

158 OWC to be tested (Table 1), and considering a water density ratio for wave flume testing of $\delta = 0.98$,
159 the air volume of the chamber at 1:25 scale should be, applying Eq.(3), $V_m = 538.4 \text{ dm}^3$. After
160 subtracting the air volume already contained inside the model chamber (25.2 dm^3) and the air volume
161 contained inside the duct that connects the chamber and the reservoir (18.2 dm^3), the air volume that
162 the reservoir has to supply is equal to 495 dm^3 . In the present application, an iron reservoir was used
163 (Figure 2), partially filled with water to remove the volume in excess of the desired one. Care must be
164 taken when designing and constructing the reservoir, as it must resist the pressures generated by the
165 OWC model without becoming deformed, which if happened would introduce undesired effects into
166 the system; similarly, the duct diameter should not be too small.

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Figure 2. Photographs of (A) a general view of the air reservoir and its connection duct; (B) a detailed view of the connection of the duct to the OWC chamber; and (C) detail of the incompressible set-up without air reservoir.

171 *2.1.1. Experimental testing programme and set-up*

172 In order to thoroughly characterise the performance of the OWC, a total of 55 regular wave conditions
 173 were tested, resulting from the combination of five wave heights (H), from $H = 0.02$ m to $H = 0.10$ m,
 174 in increments of 0.02 m (from $H = 0.5$ m to $H = 2.5$ m, in prototype dimensions) and eleven wave
 175 periods (T), from $T = 1.0$ s to $T = 3.0$ s, in increments of 0.2 s (from $T = 5.0$ s to $T = 15.0$ s, in
 176 prototype dimensions). The water depth (h) was set to 0.42 m ($h = 10.5$ m, in prototype dimensions).
 177 The 55 wave conditions were tested for the three aforementioned orifice diameters ($D = 28, 31$ and 39

178 mm), representative of three different values of the turbine-induced damping. In addition, tests were
179 carried out under two different set-ups: (i) taking into account the air compressibility effects by
180 scaling the chamber air volume proportionally to the square of the scale factor, Eq.(3), (i.e.,
181 connecting the air chamber to the air reservoir); and (ii) assuming air incompressibility at model scale
182 by scaling the chamber air volume with the cube of the scale factor (i.e., disconnecting the air
183 reservoir). In total, the experimental campaign comprised 330 tests.

184 Tests were carried out in the wave flume of the University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain.
185 The flume is 20 m long, 0.95 m high and 0.65 m wide. A piston-type paddle, equipped with an active
186 wave absorption system, *DHI AWACS* (Schäffer and Jakobsen, 2003), that prevents re-reflections of
187 incoming waves, was used for wave generation. The experimental set-up is presented in Figure 3. The
188 OWC model was located at 10.30 m from the paddle, with the air reservoir placed at the rear top of
189 the chamber. Free surface elevation was measured using nine *DHI-202* resistance wave gauges (WGs)
190 distributed along the flume (Figure 3). The measurements of the gauges enabled the monitoring of the
191 incident waves (WG1), the analysis of the incident and reflected waves fields (WG2-5), the
192 verification the waves approaching the model (WG6), and the verification of the absence of transverse
193 waves (WG7-9). Additionally, two *Omega-LVU31* ultrasonic level sensors (US1 and US2) were
194 placed inside the chamber to record the oscillations of the water column. Both types of level sensors,
195 resistance wave gauges and ultrasonic level sensors, have resolutions below 1 mm with an accuracy of
196 millimetres. Finally, the pressure drop between the interior of the chamber and the atmosphere was
197 measured by means of a *GE-Druck-LPM5480* differential pressure sensor (PS), with a range of
198 ± 2000 Pa and accuracy of $\pm 0.25\%$ of full scale. The sampling frequency of all the measurement
199 instrumentation was 20 Hz.

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Figure 3. Experimental set-up.

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The main caveat when considering air compressibility is the measurement of the air flow rate that, after taking into account the air compressibility, cannot be directly calculated from the motions of the free surface within the chamber. The first attempt was to use an air flow rate meter—hence the use of the duct. Nevertheless, the operational conditions are very demanding (bidirectional flow of relatively high frequency, variable range and high accuracy requirements) and the checked solutions did not show a successful performance. The most common alternative is the calibration of the orifice in order to obtain the relation between the pressure drop and the circulating air flow rate (Sarmiento, 1993; Sheng, W. *et al.*, 2013). In this case, the calibration was accomplished through numerical modelling.

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Given the small values of the pressure drop ratio (defined as the ratio between the pressure drop through the orifice and the absolute pressure on the inlet side) achieved in the model tests, the expansibility factor of air (Y), which corrects for expansion effects when a compressible fluid passes through an orifice, would become very close to unity, $Y > 0.99$ (Reader-Harris, 2015), which means that the calibration of the orifice remains constant regardless of the air compressibility. This fact enables an incompressible numerical model to be used to calibrate the orifice. Once calibrated, the obtained curves allowed the air flow rate to be computed in the physical model directly from the pressure drop measurements.

219 2.2. Numerical modelling

220 The open-source computational fluid dynamics (CFD) package OpenFOAM[®] (version 4.1) was used
221 for modelling the OWC. It is a bundle of different C++ libraries capable of solving a wide variety of
222 continuum mechanics problems (Jasak *et al.*, 2007). Among the different solvers included in the
223 OpenFOAM[®] package, for solving the motions of the interface between two incompressible phases
224 the *interFoam* solver was used. OpenFOAM[®] has been successfully used and validated to deal with
225 OWC modelling, both to analyse the hydrodynamics of the device (Vyzikas, Deshoulières, Giroux *et*
226 *al.*, 2017) and to optimise the geometry and the turbine-induced damping (Simonetti *et al.*, 2017).

227 2.2.1. Governing equations

228 The numerical model solves the Reynolds averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations, which describe
229 the flow motion of a fluid. The RANS equations consist of a mass conservation equation, Eq.(5), and
230 a momentum conservation equation, Eq.(6), expressed as:

$$231 \quad \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad , \quad (5)$$

$$232 \quad \frac{\partial \rho u_i}{\partial t} + u_j \frac{\partial \rho u_i}{\partial x_j} = - \frac{\partial p^*}{\partial x_i} - g_i X_j \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\mu_{eff} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} \right] + f_{\sigma,i} \quad , \quad (6)$$

233 where $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ denote the Cartesian components of the three-dimensional vectors or tensors; u_i is
234 the i th component of the velocity vector; ρ is the density of the fluid; p^* is the pseudo-dynamic
235 pressure; g_i is i th component of the gravitational acceleration; X_i is the position vector; μ_{eff} is the
236 effective dynamic viscosity ($\mu_{eff} = \mu + \rho \nu_t$, where μ is the molecular dynamic viscosity and ν_t is the
237 turbulent kinematic viscosity given by the turbulence model); finally, $f_{\sigma,i}$ is the i th component of the
238 surface tension tensor term.

239 As mentioned above, a turbulence model which provide a value for the turbulent kinematic
240 viscosity is needed for the closure of the equations. In this case, the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model was
241 used. This model combines the best features of the $k-\epsilon$ and $k-\omega$ models showing good results in
242 simulating OWC devices (Iturrioz *et al.*, 2015), other wave energy conversion technologies (Schmitt
243 and Elsaesser, 2015) and also wave-structure interaction problems in coastal engineering (Higuera *et*
244 *al.*, 2013).

245 The movements of the interface between the air and water phases was tracked by the volume-of-
246 fluid (VOF) method (Hirt and Nichols, 1981). This method uses a phase-fraction function (α) defined
247 as the fraction of the cell volume filled with water: for a cell full of water the phase-fraction function

248 takes a value of $\alpha = 1$, for a cell full of air $\alpha = 0$, and $0 < \alpha < 1$ for an interface cell which contains
 249 both air and water. The tracking of the free surface movements is modelled by means of the following
 250 advection equation:

$$251 \quad \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_i \alpha}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial u_{c,i} \alpha (1 - \alpha)}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (7)$$

252 where the last term on the left-hand-side is an artificial compression term (Deshpande *et al.*, 2012)
 253 introduced to achieve a sharper interface, being $u_{c,i}$ the artificial compression velocity.

254 For wave generation and absorption, the relaxation technique included in the *waves2Foam*
 255 toolbox was used (Jacobsen *et al.*, 2012). This technique forms part of the internal wave generation
 256 methods, in which waves are generated within a region defined inside the numerical domain. In
 257 addition, the relaxation zones enable passive wave absorption to avoid reflection of waves into the
 258 computational domain. Thus, wave generation and absorption are accomplished by modifying the
 259 velocity, pressure and phase-fraction function inside the relaxation zone following:

$$260 \quad \phi = \alpha_R \phi_{computed} + (1 - \alpha_R) \phi_{target}, \quad (8)$$

261 where ϕ represents any flow variable in the relaxation zone for which the solution will be a weighted
 262 combination of the numerical model solution and a target or desired solution forced over the
 263 relaxation zone; and α_R is the relaxation function, defined as (Jacobsen *et al.*, 2012):

$$264 \quad \alpha_R(\chi_R) = 1 - \frac{\exp(\chi_R^{3.5}) - 1}{\exp(1) - 1} \quad \text{for } \chi_R \in [0, 1], \quad (9)$$

265 where χ_R is the coordinate along the x -axis scaled to the length of the relaxation zone.

266 2.2.2. Computational domain

267 The numerical model faithfully reproduces the experimental set-up, with the differences inherent to
 268 numerical wave generation through relaxation zones, that is, the numerical wave flume incorporates
 269 an upstream extra section—the relaxation zone region (Figure 4)—where waves are generated and
 270 absorbed, emulating the wave generation and absorption system of the experimental wave flume.

271 There is no outlet relaxation zone as no waves go beyond the OWC model; for the same reason, the
 272 numerical flume ends just behind the OWC. Furthermore, the numerical model takes advantage of a
 273 symmetry boundary condition to only simulate one half of the flume, which brings important
 274 computational cost savings. The length of the computational domain from the end of the relaxation
 275 zone (where wave propagation starts) to the front wall of the OWC model was set, as in the
 276 experimental set-up, to 10.30 m.

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Figure 4. Computational domain. The boundary conditions are indicated in capital letters.

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The computational domain was spatially discretised using the *snappyHexMesh* utility, a mesh generator which, starting from a simple background mesh that is iteratively refined and morphed, outputs a hexahedral mesh conformed to a given geometric surface. Attending to the characteristics of the mesh, four main regions can be distinguished (Figure 4): the relaxation region, the propagation region, the transition region and the model-testing region. In the three first regions (relaxation, propagation and transition regions) the mesh is parameterised based on the wave conditions to be simulated, i.e., the cell size varies depending on the wave height and the wave period. The characteristics of the model-testing zone, however, remains constant despite changes in the wave conditions. With this methodology of different mesh regions, a uniform grid with a cell aspect ratio equal to one—optimum for the performance of the *snappyHexMesh* utility—can be generated in the location of the OWC model, without affecting the mesh of the remaining domain. The computational mesh is presented in Figure 5.

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Figure 5. Computational mesh: (A) general view of the numerical wave flume; (B) detail of the mesh around the free surface; (C) detail of the mesh around the outlet of the orifice; (D) detail of the mesh around the entrance of the chamber; (E) perspective view zoomed in the model-testing region; (F) slice orthogonal to the y -axis at $y = 0$ (symmetry boundary); and (G) slice orthogonal to the x -axis at $x = 10.384$ m (x -coordinate of the centre of the orifice).

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In the propagation region, the mesh is uniform along the x -axis, with a cell size that ensures 50 cells per wavelength, a value already used in similar applications (Vanneste and Troch, 2015). As mentioned above, the length of this region is constant in order to faithfully reproduce the experimental set-up; therefore, following previous works (López, I. *et al.*, 2014), a non-uniform mesh was set along the z -axis, with a finer sub-mesh around the free surface. The minimum cell size was set to $\Delta z = 0.005$ m for $H = 0.04$ - 0.06 m, and to $\Delta z = 0.010$ m for $H = 0.08$ - 0.10 m, to match the ratio $H/\Delta z \geq 8$ (Simonetti *et al.*, 2017). For the smallest waves ($H = 0.02$ m) it was found that a ratio $H/\Delta z \geq 2$ is enough (Vanneste and Troch, 2015), so the cell size was set to $\Delta z = 0.005$ m. As the distance to the free surface increases, the cell size is doubled successively, maintaining the cell size constant during, at least, three layers. The growth is faster towards the air domain where a maximum cell size of $\Delta z = 0.08$ m was set. Those settings, both on the x - and z -axis, were maintained in the relaxation region, whose total length was established to one wavelength, a solution successfully employed in upstream relaxation zones (e.g., Hu *et al.*, 2016; Simonetti *et al.*, 2017). The z -axis settings of the propagation region were maintained, again, in the transition region. However, along the x -axis a growing rate was established to ensure a smooth transition from the cell size in the

312 propagation region to that in the model-testing region. The total length of the transition region was set
313 to 0.3 wavelength. In these three regions, the cell size in the y -axis was set to $\Delta y = 0.04$ m, resulting in
314 8 cells along this axis; which is enough as no meaningful flow is expected in this direction.

315 Finally, in the un-parametrized mesh of the model-testing region a base cell size of
316 $\Delta x = \Delta y = \Delta z = 0.04$ m was used. This base size was refined progressively in all directions (using up
317 to five refinement levels) in the proximity of the OWC model contours to obtain a mesh that better fits
318 the model. A minimum of two cell layers of each size was established to improve the mesh
319 smoothness. The area in the interior of the chamber and at the front of the OWC model was refined to
320 $\Delta x = \Delta y = \Delta z = 0.01$ m and at the free surface to $\Delta x = \Delta y = \Delta z = 0.005$ m. In addition, an extra
321 refinement was made in the orifice duct and its inlet and outlet area matching that of the free surface.

322 The boundary conditions were set to *wall* for the bottom, left-side, and rear boundaries, as well
323 as for all the boundaries of the OWC model (Figure 4). The *wall* boundary condition implies no-slip
324 condition for velocity, zero-gradient conditions for pressure and phase-fraction function, and special
325 wall functions for k and ω according to the k - ω SST turbulence model. At the *inlet*, special wave
326 generating functions were implemented for velocity and phase-fraction (Jacobsen *et al.*, 2012),
327 whereas zero-gradient conditions were set for pressure. At the *atmosphere*, the pressure was set to a
328 fixed total value equal to zero, the velocity to a *pressureInletOutletVelocity* condition in which a zero-
329 gradient condition is applied for outflow, and for inflow the velocity is calculated from the flux
330 through the boundary; the phase-fraction function was set to an *inletOutlet* condition, which switches
331 between zero-gradient for outflow, and a fixed value set to zero (air), for the case of return flow.
332 Finally, the right-side of the computational domain was set to a symmetry boundary.

333 2.2.3. Numerical testing programme

334 The aim of the numerical tests is the calibration of the three orifices that emulate the turbines. Given
335 that the pressure-vs-flow-rate depends on the characteristics of the orifice, and not on the wave
336 conditions that forced them (Sheng, W., Thiebaut *et al.*, 2013), calibrating the orifices for the whole
337 set of wave conditions is not necessary. In any case, a heterogeneous selection of nine wave
338 conditions were tested to prove the previous statement, covering five different wave periods and five
339 wave heights (Table 2).

340

Table 2. Wave conditions included in the numerical testing programme.

Wave condition	Model dimensions		Prototype dimensions	
	<i>T</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>H</i>
#1	1.20 s	0.06 m	6 s	1.5 m
#2	1.60 s	0.02 m	8 s	0.5 m
#3	1.60 s	0.04 m	8 s	1.0 m
#4	1.60 s	0.06 m	8 s	1.5 m
#5	1.60 s	0.08 m	8 s	2.0 m
#6	1.60 s	0.10 m	8 s	2.5 m
#7	2.00 s	0.06 m	10 s	1.5 m
#8	2.40 s	0.06 m	12 s	1.5 m
#9	2.80 s	0.06 m	14 s	1.5 m

341 However, the first milestone when dealing with numerical modelling is the validation. In this
342 case, it was carried out through the comparison between the experimental measurements (from the
343 incompressible set-up) and the numerical model data. The heterogeneity of the wave conditions
344 selected for the numerical programme ensure a meaningful validation without reproducing the whole
345 experimental set. In order to validate the model, both the pressure drop between the interior of the
346 chamber and the atmosphere, and the oscillations of the water column were measured. Additionally,
347 the free surface elevations along the flume were measured at the same positions defined in the
348 experimental set-up (Figure 3). The flow rate through the orifice was also measured for calibrating the
349 orifice.

350 The performance of the numerical model for each wave condition was evaluated on the basis of
351 the correlation coefficient and the normalised root mean square error (Appendix A).

352 2.3. Data analysis

353 Once the numerical model was validated, the next step was to obtain the calibration curves of the
354 three orifices. For each numerical test, the data points of pressure drop versus flow rate were fitted
355 with a parabolic curve centred at the origin (López, I. *et al.*, 2016) that can be expressed, for
356 exhalation stage ($\Delta p > 0$) by:

$$357 \Delta p = B_{exh} Q^2, \quad (10)$$

358 and for inhalation stage ($\Delta p < 0$) by:

$$359 \Delta p = -(B_{inh}) Q^2, \quad (11)$$

360 where Δp is the pressure drop between the interior of the chamber and the atmosphere, Q is the flow
361 rate and B is a damping parameter. The damping parameters for each orifice were calculated as the
362 average of the nine damping parameter values obtained from the wave conditions tested. Given the
363 closeness between the inhalation and exhalation values, a representative damping parameter (B_r) was

364 subsequently calculated as the average of the values of both stages. Finally, based on previous works
 365 (López, I. *et al.*, 2014), a dimensionless damping coefficient was defined as:

$$366 \quad B^* = \frac{\Delta p^{1/2}}{Q} \frac{A_c}{\rho_a^{1/2}} = B_r^{1/2} \frac{A_c}{\rho_a^{1/2}} , \quad (12)$$

367 where A_c is the plant area of the OWC chamber ($A_c = l_c \times w_c$); and ρ_a is the air density. The damping
 368 coefficient is, therefore, a dimensionless parameter that characterises the turbine-induced damping.

369 From the numerical obtained damping parameters of the three orifices and the experimental
 370 pressure drop data, the instantaneous flow rate for each one of the 330 experimental tests was
 371 calculated following:

$$372 \quad Q = \text{sgn}(\Delta p) \left(\frac{|\Delta p|}{B_r} \right)^{1/2} . \quad (13)$$

373 Known the instantaneous pressure drop and the flow rate, the mean pneumatic power is given
 374 by:

$$375 \quad P_p = \frac{1}{t_{max}} \int_0^{t_{max}} \Delta p Q dt . \quad (14)$$

376 Once the pneumatic power is calculated, the second key variable to evaluate the performance of
 377 an OWC is the wave power. First, the incident and reflected wave fields were obtained by means of a
 378 reflection analysis carried out using the Mansard and Funke (Mansard and Funke, 1980) method
 379 modified by Baquerizo (1995). Second, based on the incident wave spectrum the mean power of the
 380 incident waves per unit width of converter was computed as:

$$381 \quad P_w = \rho_w g \int_0^\infty S(\omega) c_g(\omega) d\omega , \quad (15)$$

382 where ρ_w is the water density; $S(\omega)$ is the spectral density; and c_g is the group velocity, defined as:

$$383 \quad c_g = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{2kh}{\sinh(2kh)} \right) \frac{\omega}{k} , \quad (16)$$

384 where k is the wave number; h is the water depth; and ω is the angular frequency, which is obtained
 385 from the dispersion relationship:

$$386 \quad \omega^2 = gk \tanh(kh) . \quad (17)$$

387 Finally, the capture width ratio (also known as relative capture width) of the OWC, i.e., the
 388 efficiency in transforming the power of the incoming waves into pneumatic power, is defined as:

$$389 \quad C_{WR} = \frac{P_p}{w_c P_w} . \quad (18)$$

390 where w_c is the width of the OWC chamber (Figure 1).

391 **3. Results and discussion**

392 3.1. Numerical model validation

393 The results of the numerical model validation for the pressure drop and the free surface elevation
 394 inside the OWC chamber are summarised in Table 3. Excellent agreement is found, with an average
 395 value of the correlation coefficient for the entire validation set close to unity and a NRMSE well
 396 below 10%, both for pressure drop ($R = 0.992$, NRMSE = 7.29%) and free surface elevation
 397 ($R = 0.986$, NRMSE = 5.90%). Although a slight performance decrease is observed when the orifice
 398 diameter increases, the results are good and consistent for the three orifice diameters tested.
 399 Comparing the results between the pressure drop and free surface elevation signals, a better agreement
 400 is found for the latter, as shows the lower value of the NRMSE: 7.29% for pressure drop vs 5.90% for
 401 the free surface elevation. The magnitude of the errors is of the same order of those achieved in
 402 previous OWC numerical models, either using an OpenFOAM® code (e.g., Simonetti *et al.*, 2017) or
 403 different commercial codes (e.g., López, I. *et al.*, 2014).

404 Table 3. Results of the numerical model validation based on the comparison between the experimental
 405 and numerical signals of pressure drop (Δp) and free surface elevation inside the OWC chamber (η_{owc}).

D (mm)	Δp				η_{owc}			
	R		NRMSE		R		NRMSE	
	average	s	average	s	average	s	average	s
28	0.9922	0.0044	0.0680	0.0186	0.9878	0.0044	0.0547	0.0131
31	0.9956	0.0073	0.0645	0.0204	0.9867	0.0050	0.0592	0.0117
39	0.9878	0.0097	0.0861	0.0316	0.9844	0.0113	0.0632	0.0159
	0.9919	0.0079	0.0729	0.0252	0.9863	0.0074	0.0590	0.0136

406 The excellent agreement is qualitatively illustrated in Figure 6, which shows the superposition of
 407 the pressure drop and free surface elevation inside the chamber from both models, physical and
 408 numerical. For clarity, only 10 s of simulation are presented. The agreement found is, again, very
 409 good. Thus, both the amplitude and the period of the pressure drop and the water column oscillations
 410 are well reproduced by the numerical model for the three orifice diameters tested. As was previously
 411 found by means of the NRMSE, the performance of the model is shown to better reproduce the free
 412 surface elevations of the water column than the pressure drop, with the amplitude of the latter slightly
 413 overpredicted. It should also be noted, that the phase between both signals is well reproduced by the
 414 numerical model too, which is paramount for a correct reproduction of the pressure-vs-flow-rate
 415 curves.

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Figure 6. Pressure drop (black) and free surface elevations of the water column inside the chamber (red) corresponding to a wave condition with $H = 0.06$ m and $T = 1.6$ s, for the three orifice diameters tested (— numerical model; \circ physical model).

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Furthermore, the time series of free surface elevations obtained from the physical and numerical models at two positions, one at the middle of the flume and the other in front of the OWC model, i.e., at WG4 and WG6 (Figure 3), are also compared, first, in Figure 7, for the wave condition with the smallest wave height ($H = 0.02$ m; $T = 1.6$ s), and second, in Figure 8, for the wave condition with the largest wave height ($H = 0.10$ m; $T = 1.6$ s). The agreement found for both wave conditions is, as in the previous validation cases, excellent. Both the wave height and period are well reproduced by the numerical model all along the flume, as show the matching between the signals measured and computed at WG4 and WG6 positions. In general, the agreement is slightly higher for the smaller waves, which is probably due to their being better represented through linear theory. Interestingly, it can be seen that the amplitude of the wave profiles varies depending on the diameter of the orifice considered. This is due to the different energy absorption of the OWC for each orifice and, consequently, to the variation in existing reflected waves.

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Figure 7. Time series of free surface elevation (η) at WG4 and WG6 positions, corresponding to a wave condition with $H = 0.02$ m and $T = 1.6$ s, for the three orifice diameters tested.

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Figure 8. Time series of free surface elevation (η) at WG4 and WG6 positions, corresponding to a wave condition with $H = 0.10$ m and $T = 1.6$ s, for the three orifice diameters tested.

438 The quantitative results of the validation of the free surface elevation at WG4 and WG6 positions
 439 are presented in Table 4. The average value of the correlation coefficient is, for the two wave
 440 conditions and at both positions, close to unity ($R > 0.98$). Similarly, the NRMSE is well below 10%,
 441 both for the smallest and the largest wave, although it is slightly higher in the case of the latter.

442 Table 4. Results of the numerical model validation based on the comparison between the experimental
 443 and numerical signals of free surface elevation at two positions along the flume (η_{WG4} and η_{WG6}), for two
 444 different wave conditions.

<i>D</i> (mm)	<i>H</i> = 0.02 m, <i>T</i> = 1.6 s				<i>H</i> = 0.10 m, <i>T</i> = 1.6 s			
	η_{WG4}		η_{WG6}		η_{WG4}		η_{WG6}	
	<i>R</i>	NRMSE	<i>R</i>	NRMSE	<i>R</i>	NRMSE	<i>R</i>	NRMSE
28	0.9983	0.0635	0.9960	0.0379	0.9952	0.0816	0.9886	0.0806
31	0.9974	0.0665	0.9948	0.0443	0.9967	0.0859	0.9863	0.0835
39	0.9857	0.0718	0.9839	0.0708	0.9950	0.0823	0.9884	0.0776
	0.9938	0.0673	0.9916	0.0510	0.9956	0.0833	0.9878	0.0806

445 All in all, the results of the validation process demonstrate that the numerical model
 446 implemented accurately reproduces the behaviour of an OWC wave energy converter under different
 447 values of the turbine-induced damping.

448 3.2. Orifice calibration curves

449 Once validated, the numerical model was used to extract the pressure-vs-flow-rate curves for the three
 450 orifice diameters, corresponding to three different values of the turbine-induced damping. The data
 451 points and the parabolic curves which fit them for each one of the orifice diameters are presented in
 452 Figure 9. The values of the representative damping parameter for each damping condition are
 453 presented in Table 5.

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Figure 9. Data points of pressure drop vs flow rate and the corresponding parabolic curves (inhalation and exhalation) for the three orifice diameters tested: (1) $D = 28$ mm; (2) $D = 31$ mm; and (3) $D = 39$ mm.

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The agreement between the dataset and the fitted curves is very good, which confirms the quadratic pressure-vs-flow-rate relationship. Furthermore, it indicates that the damping parameters are consistent regardless of the wave height and wave period. This statement is also corroborated by the low values of the standard deviation presented in Table 5. Given the small difference between the inhalation and exhalation values of the damping parameter, the use of an average representative value for both stages (B_r) is justified.

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Table 5. Inhalation, exhalation and representative values of the damping parameter (B) for the three orifice diameters tested.

D (mm)	B_{inh} (kg/m ⁷)		B_{exh} (kg/m ⁷)		B_r (kg/m ⁷)
	average	s	average	s	average
28	5.33×10^6	9.72×10^4	5.27×10^6	8.24×10^4	5.30×10^6
31	3.59×10^6	7.54×10^4	3.59×10^6	6.86×10^4	3.59×10^6
39	1.48×10^6	3.59×10^4	1.48×10^6	3.77×10^4	1.48×10^6

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Finally, the values of the dimensionless damping coefficient for the three orifice diameters, $D = 28, 31$ and 39 mm, calculated through Eq. (12), are $B^* = 160.49, 132.18$ and 84.85 , respectively.

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3.3. Air compressibility effects

The values of the capture width ratio calculated for the 55 wave conditions tested under three damping conditions and two different set-ups, incompressible (assuming full geometric similarity) and compressible (scaling correctly the chamber air volume by enlarging it through an air reservoir), are presented in Figure 10. The effects of the air compressibility can be easily evaluated by comparing

473 the first and second column of graphs, or directly in the graphs of the third column which show the
 474 relative difference in the C_{WR} between the incompressible and compressible set-up.

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476 Figure 10. In the first and second column of graphs, variation of the capture width ratio (C_{WR}) with the
 477 wave height (H) and the wave period (T) under the three damping conditions tested, for the
 478 incompressible (first column) and compressible (second column) set-ups; in the third column, variation
 479 of the relative difference between the capture width ratio of the compressible set-up with respect to the
 480 incompressible one.

481 First, it could be interesting to analyse separately each set-up, incompressible and compressible.

482 In the incompressible set-up (Figure 10 – left column), the results point that, for the OWC model
 483 tested, there is a resonant period (an optimum period which maximises the C_{WR}) in the vicinity of
 484 $T = 1.20-1.40$ s, that substantially improves the C_{WR} ; and the maximum performance is achieved for
 485 the lower wave heights. Second, the influence of the wave height is much more complex: for wave
 486 periods close to the resonant, the higher the wave height, the lower the C_{WR} ; on the contrary, for larger
 487 periods far away from the resonant (around $T = 3.0$ s), the higher the wave height, the greater the C_{WR} .
 488 For intermediate periods (around $T = 2.0$ s), the influence of the variation in wave height is much
 489 lower, producing only slight variations in the C_{WR} . Third, the damping, known to be a critical

490 parameter on the performance of an OWC (López, I. *et al.*, 2015), plays also an important role: an
491 appropriate selection can improve the maximum capture width ratio from $C_{WR} < 60\%$ for the higher
492 damping ($B^* = 160.49$) to $C_{WR} > 80\%$ for the lower damping ($B^* = 84.85$). There is not, though, a
493 damping condition that is optimum for every wave condition, it varies depending on the wave height
494 and period combination. All these findings are in accordance with those provided by previous works
495 (e.g., López, I. *et al.*, 2015; Rezanejad *et al.*, 2017), contributing again to validate the methodology
496 followed in this work.

497 Attending to the compressible set-up (Figure 10 – centre column), overall, all the previous
498 results remain valid. This fact gives relevance to the incompressible testing, which constitutes a valid
499 approach to obtain a general view of the performance of an OWC wave energy converter. However, a
500 careful comparative analysis points out subtle differences. In this way, in the incompressible set-up,
501 the resonant period changes depending both on the damping conditions and on the wave height. When
502 the damping coefficient increases, the resonant period changes towards greater wave periods, e.g., for
503 $B^* = 84.85$ and $H = 0.02$ m, the resonant period is $T = 1.20$ s, whereas for $B^* = 160.49$ and $H =$
504 0.02 m, the resonant period increases to $T = 1.40$ s. Moreover, it can be seen that the resonant period
505 also moves to greater values when the wave height increases, e.g., for $H = 0.02$ m and $B^* = 132.18$ the
506 resonant period is $T = 1.40$ s, whereas for $H = 0.10$ m and $B^* = 132.18$, the resonant period increases
507 to $T = 1.60$ s. This behaviour becomes more evident for the greater values of the damping coefficient.
508 In the compressible set-up, however, the resonant period remains constant at the same value
509 ($T = 1.20$ s) independently of both the damping conditions and the wave height.

510 More importantly, the capture width ratio is also altered by the air compressibility effects, as
511 indicates the relative difference between the C_{WR} of the compressible set-up with respect to the
512 incompressible one (Figure 10 – right column). The results show that the influence of the air
513 compressibility on the capture width ratio highly depends on the wave conditions. Thus, for the
514 smaller wave periods ($T < 1.20$ s), the air compressibility exerts a positive influence on the C_{WR} , with
515 improvements on the performance of the OWC higher than 30%. On the contrary, for greater periods
516 ($T > 1.20$ s), the air compressibility produces a reduction of the C_{WR} up to -28.2% . In addition, the
517 damping plays an important role, mainly for the wave conditions of $T > 1.20$ s: for the greater value of
518 the damping coefficient ($B^* = 160.49$), air compressibility negatively impacts the C_{WR} for practically
519 the whole range of wave heights; nevertheless, for the lower value of the damping coefficient
520 ($B^* = 84.85$), the air compressibility effects are positive from the point of view of the C_{WR} for the

521 wave conditions with lower wave heights ($H < 0.06$ m). For these waves with greater period
 522 ($T > 1.20$ s), overall, the greater the wave height, the greater the negative impact of the air
 523 compressibility effects. This result is related to the findings of Simonetti *et al.*, (2018), who point that
 524 scaling effects due to air compressibility become more important as the pressure drop increases (in
 525 general, higher wave heights produce greater oscillations of the water column and, therefore, greater
 526 pressure differences).

527 Complementarily to the previous analysis, it is also interesting to establish the overall influence
 528 of air compressibility, by averaging the capture width ratio over the whole set of wave conditions for
 529 both set-ups, incompressible and compressible (Table 6). The relative difference between the global
 530 average values of the capture width ratio between the incompressible and compressible set-ups is
 531 about 10% for the greater values of the damping coefficient ($B^* = 132.18$ and 160.49), drastically
 532 changing for the lower damping condition ($B^* = 84.85$) under which the relative difference is positive
 533 and greater than 3%. Therefore, it is shown, again, that the damping plays an important role in the
 534 performance of an OWC converter, determining the direction of the overall influence of the air
 535 compressibility effects on the capture width ratio. Furthermore, when air compressibility effects are
 536 taken into account the optimum damping coefficient (i.e., that which maximises the C_{WR} for the whole
 537 set of wave conditions) changes: the optimum damping coefficient for the incompressible set-up is the
 538 intermediate one ($B^* = 132.18$), whereas for the compressible set-up is the lowest ($B^* = 84.85$). This
 539 is of paramount importance given that a wrong evaluation of the optimum damping could lead to a
 540 wrong dimensioning of the turbine (Pereiras *et al.*, 2015).

541 Table 6. Global average values of the capture width ratio (C_{WR}) considering the whole set of
 542 wave conditions, for the three values of the damping coefficient.

B^*	C_{WR}		<i>Relative difference (%)</i>
	<i>incompressible set-up</i>	<i>compressible set-up</i>	
160.49	0.278	0.250	-9.99
132.18	0.284	0.261	-8.08
84.85	0.256	0.265	+3.58

543 In the recent literature, only a couple of works focused on the effects of the air compressibility
 544 on the performance of an OWC considering non-linear effects (i.e., without analytical simplifications
 545 of the governing processes), both carried out by numerical modelling (Elhanafi *et al.*, 2017; Simonetti
 546 *et al.*, 2018). For the testing conditions (wave height, wave period and damping conditions)
 547 considered in these works, overestimations of the OWC performance in the order of 10% was found
 548 when air compressibility effects are disregarded. These works, however, only point to a negative

549 impact of the air compressibility, which is probably related to the reduced range of testing conditions
550 considered. In any case, despite the limited conditions tested, Elhanafi *et al.* (2017) highlighted that
551 the overestimation in OWC efficiency is more pronounced for wave periods larger than the resonant,
552 and noted the influence of the damping conditions, results which are in line with those presented in
553 this work. The complex nature of the air compressibility effects on the OWC performance was also
554 pointed out, through an analytical model, by Falcão *et al.* (2014), who emphasise that disregarding air
555 compressibility effects leads to errors which change its sign depending on the wave period.

556 4. Conclusions

557 In this work, the influence of air compressibility on the performance of an OWC wave energy
558 converter was thoroughly evaluated through physical modelling. To take into account the air
559 compressibility, the scaling of the air volume of the OWC chamber was performed according to the
560 square of the length scale ratio ($V \propto \varepsilon^2$) using an air reservoir to provide the additional air volume
561 required. Moreover, an incompressible set-up was also tested by assuming full geometric similarity ($V \propto \varepsilon^3$), i.e., disconnecting the air reservoir. The experimental campaign involved a total of 330 tests,
562 resulting from the combination of 55 wave conditions and three different values of the turbine-
563 induced damping, tested for two different set-ups, compressible and incompressible. The flow rate
564 was calculated from pressure drop data measurements using calibrated pressure-vs-flow-rate curves
565 for each of the three orifices which represent as many damping conditions. The calibration curves
566 were obtained by means of the open source RANS-based CFD model OpenFOAM[®], coupled with the
567 *waves2Foam* toolbox for wave generation. The numerical model was successfully validated based on
568 the experimental results (pressure drop and free surface elevation inside the OWC chamber), both
569 quantitatively ($R_{average} > 0.98$, $NRMSE_{average} < 8\%$) and qualitatively (by direct comparison of the
570 measurements from both models).
571

572 Based on the results of the experimental campaign, the following conclusions may be drawn.
573 First, the incompressible set-up (i.e., full geometric similarity by scaling the air chamber volume to
574 the cube of the length scale ratio) constitutes a useful approach to study an OWC in its early stages of
575 development, for it leads to findings broadly similar to those obtained with the compressible set-up:
576 (i) existence of a resonant period that maximises the capture width ratio (C_{WR}); (ii) significant
577 influence of the damping on the C_{WR} ; and (iii) complex influence of the wave height on the C_{WR} ,
578 mainly governed by the wave period. However, disregarding air compressibility introduces spurious

579 variations of the resonant period when testing conditions change and, more importantly, leads to
580 wrong estimates of the capture width ratio. Thus, although using an incompressible set-up could be a
581 valid approach in the early stages of design, it must be avoided when an in-depth analysis of the
582 performance of the OWC is required.

583 Second, the air compressibility effects significantly affect the efficiency of the OWC, altering the
584 C_{WR} with respect to that of the incompressible set-up, approximately, in the range of -30 to 30 per
585 cent, depending, mainly, on the wave conditions. Thus, air compressibility effects are highly
586 influenced by the sea state. In general, disregarding air compressibility leads to underpredictions of
587 the C_{WR} for periods below the resonant period, and to overpredictions for larger periods. Furthermore,
588 it was shown that the damping plays a fundamental role in the performance of an OWC converter,
589 determining the direction and magnitude of the overall influence of the air compressibility effects on
590 the C_{WR} . It was also found that the optimum damping coefficient (critical parameter for dimensioning
591 the turbine) decreases when air compressibility effects are taken into account; it follows that
592 neglecting air compressibility could well lead to suboptimal specifications for the turbine. As a final
593 remark, air compressibility effects are complex and, consequently, do not lend themselves to a
594 simplification in the form of an overall percentage value – the variation of the performance of the
595 OWC over the entire range of operating conditions must be considered.

596 In sum, the spring-like effect of air compressibility in the chamber is important in an OWC wave
597 energy converter. Should this effect be disregarded, significant errors would be introduced in the
598 assessment of the device efficiency, including both under- and over-predictions, depending on the sea
599 state and the turbine-induced damping. In light of these results, it may be concluded that air
600 compressibility must be considered in all but the preliminary stages of design or analysis.

601 **Acknowledgements**

602 During this work I. López was supported by the postdoctoral grant ED481B 2016/125-0 of the
603 ‘Programa de Axudas á etapa posdoutoral da Xunta de Galicia (Consellería de Cultura, Educación e
604 Ordenación Universitaria)’, and G. Iglesias benefited from a Marie Curie Individual Fellowship
605 (WAVEIMPACT, PCIG13-GA-2013-618556). The authors are indebted to the Centre for
606 Supercomputing of Galicia (CESGA), Spain, for the use of high-performance computational resources
607 and the support in performing the numerical simulations.

608 **Appendix A. Error estimators**

609 The performance of the numerical model for each wave condition was evaluated on the basis of the
610 correlation coefficient, defined as:

$$611 \quad R = \frac{s_{xy}}{s_x s_y} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

612 where s_{xy} represents the covariance between the measurements from the experimental tests and the
613 corresponding values from the numerical model tests; and s_x and s_y represent the sample standard
614 deviation of the experimental and numerical tests, respectively. Additionally, the normalised root
615 mean square error was also calculated as:

$$616 \quad \text{NRMSE} = \frac{1}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - y_i)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

617 where x_i represents the i -th data element of the measurements from the experimental tests; y_i
618 represents the corresponding value from the numerical model tests; N is the total number of data
619 points; and $x_{max} - x_{min}$ represent the range of the data from the experimental test considered. It is
620 preferred over the average because of the sinusoidal nature of the data (the average is close to zero).
621

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